

Social Communication through Hashtag (#) During the Covid-19 Pandemic in Indonesia

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ABSTRACT: Aim of the study was to explain the role of the Hashtag (#) in social media as social communication channels in the Covid-19 pandemic in Indonesia. Referring to the concept of social communication by Ruben and Stewart that communication has a function, namely adapting to each other's environment or social integration, while social media becomes an online medium that strengthens the relationship between individuals / users as well as social bond (according to Van Dijk). The results show, people participate posting #tetapdirumah, #JagaJarak, #cucitangan on Indonesian social media platforms. People took part in implementing all the suggestions but not because they were encouraged by the exposure of the Hashtag (#) on their social media platforms, despite arguing that the Hashtag (#) on social media that made the issue of Covid-19 a trending, quite effectively played a role in shaping shared awareness, spread information, and educate the public how to cut off the spread of the Covid-19 virus, so it can be concluded that social communication through Hashtag (#) on social media has not been able to encourage people to adapt and changes in the social environment due to the Covid-19 pandemic.

KEYWORDS -Social Communication, Hashtag, Covid-19 Pandemic

I. Introduction

Covid-19 pandemic which also hit Indonesia led to changes in various social arrangements related to WHO standard Health protocols such as Social Distancing / Physical Distancing, using masks and Washing hands with soap properly and regularly, becoming part of people's daily activities. A significant movement in the context of adapting to the pandemic is the increasing use of communication technology as a means of communicating with the public. Utilize gadgets to access various social media platforms to communicate and meet various information needs and maximize technology applications to meet life and work needs.

No less the government also utilizes the power of mass media both conventional / mainstream and new media / social media to communicate and disseminate policies related to Covid-19 mitigation to the public. While the community welcomes and supports various policies implemented and participates in communicating through their social media channels, using language symbols in cyberspace such as Tanda pagar (#) or Hashtag as markers of the main topics of discussion about Covid-19.

In this pandemic, we will easily find and get exposure to various # (Hash signs) on social media that we can access, such as; #dirumahsaja, #wfh, #socialdistancing, #jagajarak, #dirumahlembihbaik, #stayathome, #pakemasker, #cucitangan, #sabarya, #tidakmudik. Here are some examples and many more various forms of Hashtag follow. Netizens who previously used # (tanda pagar) for specific purposes and purposes, during this pandemic can be seen in almost every post they close with # (tanda pagar) related to covid-19. What is interesting is # (tanda pagar) during this pandemic in Indonesia not only appeared on social media but also on the screen in almost all the mainstream media that we have.

Yuswohady: Initially the Hashtag was used as a tool to mark a specific comment or topic of conversation on the Twitter apps. With Hashtags tweeps (Twitter users) will easily browse certain topics with Twitter's search feature. A hashtag is a creative way carried out by the Twitter community to build collective awareness about a particular social issue or problem.(1) In the language of Clay Sirky: social media expert

from New York University, Hashtag has the powerful power to form shared awareness which can lead to concrete mass movements such as political demonstrations, awareness actions, social campaigns and so on.(2) [1]

1.1. Research Question

- 1.1.1. Is #pandemic covid-19 (all forms # covid-19 related) really able to form a "shared awareness" in our community so that it can help to cut off the spread of the covid-19 virus, consider to this day (May-June 2020) positive confirmation of covid-19 are still increasing in Indonesia.
- 1.1.2. How this # symbol in the mass media during the covid-19 pandemic can be used to build public awareness in Indonesia about the importance of maintaining health.
- 1.1.3. As a social communication channels in Indonesia community the role of social media through Hashtag (#) is it able to realize the adaptation of the community to the environment in the situation and conditions of the Covid-19 pandemic.

1.2. Research Purposes

The purpose of this research is to find out and explain the role of Hashtag (#) on social media platforms in forming "shared awareness" during the Corona Virus 19 pandemic (Covid-19) and as a social communication channel for controlling the spread of the Covid-19 virus in Indonesia.

By this paper we try to understand how people in Indonesia to take advantage of social media for social communication through hashtag # so we can give suggestion what we can do related to the effort of the process adaptation of the community to the environment in the situation and conditions of the Covid-19 pandemic.

1.3. Previous Research

In the research 'The Use of Hashtag (#) Twitter Accounts of the Directorate General of Taxes in Efforts to Build Tax Pay Awareness'Meladia,M.Nadjib and M. Akbar concluded that: First, Hashtag type is more dominant as result of retweeting and hashtag function is more grouping function. Second the contents of the Hashtag are mostly related to activities, are informative, and links are in the form of photos. And third Tweets using Hashtags on social media in online counseling activities paying tax awareness have a positive and significant influence on attention, interest, search, action, and sharing based on the results of the model tests conducted, by utilizing the features in social media, it is expected to help the government and institutions non-profits in extension activities, and public awareness campaigns.(3)[2]

Muhammad Usman Noor through his research 'Insight into Hashtags: Search for Halal Tourism Information through Hashtags #WisataHalal on Instagram' found that; Hashtags on Instagram can provide insight for potential tourists related to Halal Tourism as well as a reference and source of information and inspiration for potential tourists who want to travel halal. Information such as tour packages, attractions, religious activities, the site, and halal food can be found easily through #WisataHalal. The ease and popularity of using Instagram itself is a better value for potential tourists and managers of tourist destinations, especially in the current generation of Millennials.(4) What is certain is the use of the hashtag of #wisatahalal can be used to promote locations or attractions.[3]

II. Covid-19 Pandemic

The latest corona virus found in Wuhan, China, in December 2019 was named SARS Coronavirus 2 (SARS-CoV-2) and caused Corona Virus Disease 2019 (COVID-19). The World Health Organization (WHO) officially declared the COVID-19 corona virus as a pandemic on Wednesday (11/3/2020). According to WHO: a pandemic is the scale of the spread of disease that occurs globally throughout the world. However, this has nothing to do with changes in the characteristics of the disease. In determining an epidemic of disease

as a pandemic, WHO has no threshold in the number of deaths or infections or also the number of countries affected. (5)

The WHO's reason for determines an epidemic of disease to be a pandemic because WHO wants to give alarm to the governments of all countries of the world to increase preparedness to prevent and deal with outbreaks. This determination is based on the reason when the outbreak was declared as a pandemic, meaning that there may have been a spread in a community. For that WHO calls on all countries to detect, test, treat, isolate, track and monitor the movements of their communities. Meanwhile the WHO also warned that the establishment of an outbreak of COVID-19 as a pandemic should not be used as an excuse to worry too much. WHO: If declaring a pandemic triggers a global panic, this can defeat its goal of trying to raise awareness. (6)[4]

III. The Concept of Social Communication

Social communication is human communication (human communication) as conveyed by Ruben and Steward, where both have similar functions, namely adapting to each other's environments or social integration. According to Ruben and Steward (7) that: human communication is a process involving individuals in a relationship between individuals, groups, organizations and society that responds and creates messages to adapt to each other's environment, then social communication is a process interaction between individuals or institutions through the delivery of messages in order to build integration or social adaptation. Social Communication purposes are: Build Self Concept, Self-Actualization, obtain joy and recreation, to avoid the tension and alienation, have relationship with another people, fulfil life sustainability. (8)[5]

The development of communication technology is so rapid, making many community communication activities switch to social media by utilizing various existing platforms. Social media is internet-based online media to facilitate users in participating and communicating quickly through various platforms, such as blogs, wikis, social networks, forum, and the virtual world. According to Van Dijk: social media is a media platform that focuses on the existence of users who facilitate them in their activities and collaborations, therefore, social media can be seen as an online medium (facilitator) that reinforces the relationship between users as well as a social bond.(9)[6]

IV. Hashtag

Administrator Organic digital: Hashtags are words or phrases without spaces that begin with a hash symbol "#". Words in messages on microblogging and social networks like Twitter, Facebook, Google + or Instagram can be marked by placing "#" in front of them, for example writing articles with the addition of the #OrganixDigital hashtag.(10) With the hashtag, the information added to the hashtag as in #OrganixDigital will automatically be combined into a group of articles with the same hashtag on one page, so can help to get more information in the same topic [7] Hashtags are used to classify themes or topics that are more specific in social media. And on the other hand, hashtag also makes it easier for others to find topics that are interconnected.

A hashtag is a hash sign that serves as a meta tag for grouping data of various posts or any content in the internet world. With a hashtag, data in the internet universe can be easily archived to make it easier for users to surf the internet looking for the desired data. Hashtags (Tanda pagar) or symbols # popularized by Twitter have a big role in enlivening conversations and making an issue a trending topic on social media. Hashtags are used to index keywords or topics on Twitter and allow users to easily follow topics of interest. Bambang Gunawan: At first Hashtag (#) has functions to: make it easy to group content, expand our post, facilitate product promotion, and now the Hashtag (Tanda pagar) function has shifted, first also as an effort to increase followers and then as shared awareness.(11)[8]

V. Research Method

This type of descriptive research is qualitative, using the case study method departing from an outbreak of the corona virus as a pandemic which then impacts various problems in the community and develops a form of social communication through the use of social media and also the mainstream media. Problem analysis uses data collected through virtual interviews through Google classroom of 25 informants on April 6, 2020.

VI. Result and Discussion

The informants basically understand enough what a hashtag (#) or Tanda pagar is and how to use it for their interests and needs on the social media platform. According to fig.1, Informants are also quite aware of the existence of #pandemicovid in various forms, such as; #dirumahsaja, #lebihbaikdirumah, #cucitangan, #jagajarak, #pakemasker and many more are trending on almost all social media platforms even though most are not aware that these various forms of # also appear in mainstream / conventional / TV programs. As; #terhubungdarirumah and # MediaLawanCovid-19 in the KompasPagi Program. #LebihAmanDirumah, #JagaJarak, #BersatuLawanCorona, in Berita Satu TV or similar Hashtag (#) on Tv One broadcast and Metro Tv, also SCTV and CNN Indonesia on Trans TV, thus it can be further studied whether the role or function of the hashtag (#) in mainstream / conventional media will be the same as its function and role in online media.

As shown in the diagram above fig. 2, that on the social media platform the role of Hashtag # (Tanda pagar) related to covid19 is quite have a role in campaigning for the prevention of covid19, where through Hashtags related to covid19 people can get information about covid-19, also educate the public to understand covid-19 virus and how to prevent it, as well as helping build public awareness about the need to live a healthier way to prevent transmission of the virus by using masks, keeping a distance and washing hands frequently.

Fig.3 Most informants also think that the campaign to prevent covid-19 virus transmission through Hashtags (#) is quite effective where various # prevention of transmission of viruses that have become trending on social media has raised public awareness about the importance of efforts that must be made to stop the spread of covid19 virus by getting used to use a mask, keep a distance and diligently wash hands.

Fig.4 All informants implemented various efforts to prevent covid-19 transmission such as: work from home, learn from home, keep distance in the crowd, wear masks in public places and start diligently washing hands, but were not only encouraged because of the exposure of Hashtags (#) that flooded their social media platforms. 20% due to unavoidable situations, due to workplace office regulations or government regulations, or forced family. 8% due to self-awareness, 8% more because of fear, the rest because of getting information from

other media. While those who implement the prevention of virus transmission due to awareness of hashtags (#) is 24%.

This data becomes contradictory to the role and effectiveness of the Hashtag (#) above fig.3 and fig.2, but this does not become biased because the role is quite effective in the use of the Hashtag (#) as a campaign tool on social media limited to educating in the sense of providing understanding and knowledge of the Covid-19 virus especially related to transmission and prevention of transmission. Hashtag (#) according to its function is to facilitate us to get information or content we need on social media platforms, it can indeed help netizens to find out about the Covid-19 virus, thus the Hashtag (#) is quite instrumental in spreading information about viruses Covid19 which can lead to awareness in the community although it is not parallel to the awareness to implement it.

The informant who co-posted # Covid-19 on his social media platform fig. 5, is it #jagajarak, #WFH, #pakemasker, etc. As many as 44%, the rest did not post even though they knew this # was trending on social media. Fig. 6 Various reasons are conveyed here why they participated in posting # Covid-19. Mostly because they want to contribute and participate in this activity, participate in empathy, feel responsible, 25% due to supporting government policies in handling the spread of this virus by keeping a distance, wearing masks, and staying at home, doing various activities at home or from House. The rest is only because they want to join in or enliven it.

A topic / issue that is echoed using a Hashtag (#) on social media can easily become trending and create shared awareness, because even if someone posts a Hashtag (#) issue just because they want to go along without any tendencies, they actually contribute spread information and make people to know and aware. In the

case of the Corona 2019-2020 pandemic, the Hashtag Movement was not entirely successful, especially in our beloved Indonesia, because shared "awareness" that was disseminated was apparently not enough to motivate the public to actually implement the prevention of Covid-19 virus transmission by keeping a distance, wear a mask and get used to washing hands.

Utilization of Hashtag (#) was later withdrawn to be used also in conventional media during this pandemic, we can see the changing or fixed Hashtag (#) display on Tv news programs on TvOne, Metro Tv, BeritaSatu, also Kompas Tv and also some entertainment programs like #tetapdirumah on Trans Tv. But apparently it did not cause shared awareness.

Advances in communication technology have changed social communication in Indonesia, where communication through social media is no longer new but has become part of the daily activities of the Indonesian people. During the Covid-19 pandemic the use of various social media platforms has increased because of the provisions for #Keeping at Home, # Working from Home, # Learning at Home, # worshipping at Home. Social communication through Hashtag (#) can be felt enough, especially in the dissemination and search for information about the Covid19 virus and the Health campaign to address the spread of the Covid-19 virus. It is enough to educate the public if the problem of hoaxes can be minimized.

This study is one example related to the existence of media ecology theory according to McLuhan that: the community has developed along with the development of technology.(12) [9] Society has been influenced by electronic media vice versa society influenced the media and so the medium is the message itself. Media law states that: enhancement, obsolescence, retrieval, and recall of media shows that technology influences social communication through new technology. (13) Media Ecology Theory refers to these principles and society cannot be separated from the influence of communication technology, technology brings global land together, and technology will remain important for almost all society. Where through the media finally people learn about them-selves. Awareness of the user community who popularized the hashtag #tetapdirumah; #pakemasker; #washing hands; #TetapDirumah, is proof that today the world order can already be said to be a global village to illustrate how the media binds the world into one, political, economic, social and cultural system.

The hashtag phenomenon # in social media at the time of the pandemic covid-19 according to McLuhan is proof that the media can regulate society socially [10]. Electronic media particularly has ability to bridge cultures that cannot be communicated beforehand. Utilization of communication technology through new technology, when the pandemic covid-19 gave social awareness in becoming a means of socialization about new cultures in overcoming a pandemic. New technology affects society, and changes in society cause further changes, but the changes that are given only at the cognitive or knowledge level, have not yet reached changes in attitudes and behavior. This can be understood because the spread of hashtags in the media that are widely shared by the public, tends to still merely follows the trend, not because of the awareness of each-individual.

Conclusion

By this research we can understand that are:

- 1.4. Social communication through Hashtags (#) can create "shared awareness" during the Covid-19 virus pandemic in Indonesian community.
- 1.5. The # symbol was able to make the Covid-19 pandemic issue trending on social media, but it is not directly proportional to the creation of awareness to implement #JagaJarak, #PakeMasker, #cucitangan to Indonesian people.
- 1.6. Social communication through Hashtag (#) on social media has not been able yet to encourage people in Indonesia to adapt to changes in the social environment due to the Covid-19 pandemic.

This research cannot yet explain about the role of cultural factors in Indonesia in the process of build awareness of health and the needed of adaptation in the social environments which is changes due to the Covid-19 pandemic, so further research needs to be done related to things that can encourage people of Indonesia with their awareness to maintain health and personal hygiene and the environment by including cultural factors that can affect the process of adaptation to environmental changes due to the development of a pandemic.

By this research we can understand and knowing that we need to do more like used influencers, role model, leadership of government, for encourage community of Indonesia to increase their awareness in succession of adaptation process. Not enough only spread the terms in social media even using #.

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